

ISic3234

I.Sicily inscription 3234

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---][---]

2. [---]VI · Euty[ch][---]

3. [---][u]xori[---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493975

EDR 139340

EDCS 22200394

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a

l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. At 2004.0647

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 84

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